

Examples on Oral Communication Analysis Using Nonlinear Techniques.

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Abstract: This paper analyzes the time series obtained from the digitalization of the oral reading of a text. A control model based on the RS-232 standard is used to extract synthetic time series and to compare their different behavior. Nonlinear techniques are used in order to recognize rules and experimental behavior models. These techniques help us to understand the physical structure of communication and allow us to recognize the existence of internal rules associated with the content of the communication. The proofs made shows similarities between human voice and the binary model based on RS- 232.

Keywords: Complex Systems Oral Communication Computer Simulations Systemic scope New Method Results

Resumen: Este artículo analiza la serie temporal obtenida de la digitalización de la lectura oral de un texto. Se utiliza un modelo de control basado en el standar RS-232 para extraer series temporales sintéticas y comparar los diferentes comportamientos. Para reconocer reglas internas se utilizan técnicas de análisis no lineal y modelos de comportamiento experimental. Estas técnicas no ayudan a entender la estructura física de la comunicación y nos permiten reconocer la existencia de reglas internas asociadas al contenido de la comunicación. Las pruebas realizadas muestran similitudes entre la voz humana y el modelo binario basado en RS-232.

Palabras clave: Caos Sistemas Complejos Comunicación Oral Simulaciones por Ordenador Enfoque Sistémico Nuevo Método Resultados

1 - Introduction

In nature we can find complex systems with a great number of degrees of freedom. Nevertheless, it is often possible to obtain information of one variable of the system along a period of time. This information constitutes a time series and is representative of the underlying dynamic system. Packard (Packard1980) proposed the use of delay coordinates to obtain phase space characteristics, an idea that was subsequently supported by the embedding theorems (Whitney1936, Takens1981).

There are many techniques for processing a time series (for more information about this issue see (Schreiber1998, Grassberger1991, Abarbanel1996). A good example of reconstruction of an attractor from a time series is the method developed in the

Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction by Roux et al (Roux1983). Actually, a time series represents the evolution of the system-noise set; therefore not all degrees of freedom can be retrieved (Caspari1991).

In the process of oral communication studied in this paper a biological non-isolated system, with a great complexity, is involved. The communication elements measured here are the trace of the evolution of such a system. To study this process we will use a technique of comparison with a synthetic time series obtained from a control model (Schreiber1998) and we will extract rules for the reconstruction of the experimental behavior.

We will see the behavior of the elapsed times between waves maximums, very easily detected in a communication, and how they are related to each

other. Besides, we will work with more complex subsystems (packets) and we will observe their relationships. The General Theory of Systems postulates the existence of eventual relationships among subsystems which form the whole system. In our case, we will study the relationships between elapsed time among maximum values from the time series, t_n vs t_{n+1} , which are observables of phase space (Hegger1997). In this way, we can use embedding theorems. We will also study relationship between internal variables of packets (weights P_n) and values of following packets, by using P_n vs P_{n+1} representations.

2 - The control model

The RS-232 standard is one of the simplest and more successful communication protocols. By means of this communication protocol, bytes of information can be sent between computers. This protocol is implemented upon a physical support by identifying potential levels with logical levels. These potential levels are implemented in well-defined square waves of size and duration. In addition, they are ordered in packets with error control structures. A typical packet is composed of a bit with logical level 0, which marks the beginning of the information, followed by 8 bits of information. These bits are followed by a parity bit for error control, some stop bits with logical level 1 and an extra time between packets.

We will consider a model based on the RS-232 protocol. In our model the square waves have been substituted for triangular waves with the maximum values placed at the center of the square wave; the parity bit and the stop bits have been removed; and the extra time has been transformed into a triangular wave that grows slowly because its duration is longer than that of normal bits. This process is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Communication model RS-232 modified.

The implemented theoretical model allowed us to simulate and register the communication process with no noise. We can generate synthetic time series

simulating a sampling process. Time series like the one of successive maximum values of a variable, can provide an empirical scheme of prediction (Lorenz1963) or show rules of transition between the phase space states $x_{n+1}=F(x_n)$, which shows the organization of the studied phenomenon.

The elapsed time t_n between successive maximum values seems to be a good tool to study the periodicity of a phenomenon as complex as water dropping (Martien1985). Figure 2 represents t_n face t_{n+1} in a communication that generates 4413 maximum values. In this case, the 'content' of the communication is unimportant because the return map only reflects protocol characteristics. In Figure 2 we can observe several linear structures. The width of the horizontal structure and the height of the vertical one depend on the limits that we impose to the extra time in the model. In our case, extra times are randomly distributed between 85 and 405 units of sampled time, where a bit consists of 5 time units. The diagonal structure is due to the existence of a separator that appears between two bytes (packets) and the sizes of the structures depend on the extra times. We observe that the diagonal structure has a slope of 45° . This effect is due to the centerness of the maximum of the separator. We observe as well a small dispersion above 45° due to the fact that a packet not always begins with a bit-to-one, so that the centerness is not perfect.

On the other hand, we observe a triangular structure due to the elapsed time between bits inside a packet. Besides, the return map shows that the communication protocol is based on the existence of packets with variable separation.

Fig. 2. t_n vs t_{n+1} in a communication that have 4413 maximums

3. Human Voice

We are going to study the communication protocol of the human voice in comparison with the protocol of the modified RS-232 model.

To follow a similar procedure to that of the modified RS-232 model first we registered the human voice (male and female) during the controlled reading of a text in Spanish. The recording took

around 70 seconds and the sampling was done at 11025 Hz with 8 bits. We worked with values between 0 and 255 and, in the same way as in the previous model, we selected local maximum values. Besides, we avoided maximum values lower than 132. In this way we reduced low intensity noise. We work with such small sampling because we study the process at levels where we start to understand information. If we increase the sampling we add new effects that don't increase understanding.

The results obtained from the female case are shown in Figures 3a and 3b. The results for a male voice are similar in shape, but there are numerical differences due to the lower frequency of the male voice.

Fig. 3. The same representation that for the previous figure but for a female voice in two different scales. (a)-left panel- behavior for large time scales. (b) -right panel- small time that allows us to observe the structure with more detail.

The structures of Figures 3a and 3b are similar to those of the binary model in the time range $[0,0.006]$ with little differences. We observe a central structure at 45° associated with the existence of a separator with distances t in $[0.003,0.006]$ in the binary model. A similar structure appears in the range $[0.007,0.012]$ which can be interpreted in the same way. The fact that the vertical and horizontal structures touch each other in the diagonal can be simulated by diminishing the minimum separation between packets. In Figure 3b two classes of structures appear. These structures are reproduced in the binary model if we consider the vibrational modes of the separator. The first structure corresponds to associations of points that are related by means of $t_{i+1}=nt_i$ for $0.003 \leq t_i \leq 0.006$ and by means of $t_{i+1}=t_i/n$ for $t_i > 0.006$ with $0.003 \leq t_{i+1} \leq 0.006$ and with $n=1,2,\dots$ in the two cases. Obviously, $n=1$ is the main diagonal aforementioned. This behavior explains the vertical and horizontal structures that appear at large scales for times greater than 0.006 in Figure 3a.

A second structure parallel to the main diagonal exists and it can be simulated in the binary model implementing another alternative separator so that for some times t_n of the diagonal, in the adequate rank, we have a $t_{n+\tau}$ with fixed τ . In the case of the human voice this separation is produced with a fixed

time $\tau \cong 0.0002$ upon those times in $[0.002,0.004]$. Another possibility is that to some times $t_n - \tau$, with t_n in the diagonal, corresponds the same value t_{n+1} that would correspond to t_n .

From the return map we have an experimental behavior translatable into mathematical terms that can provide elements for the implementation of a general model.

4. Structure of packets

We will use the return map of the binary model to analyze the packets structure of oral communication. In the case of the human voice the analysis of the return map shows that for long-time scales the separator does not exist. We can reproduce this fact in our model placing separators between packets only when elapsed times are in a specific rank. Anyway, the packets structure is clear with or without separators.

We carried out a multifractal analysis of the distribution of maximum values in our model and in oral communication with the aim of finding some type of clustering on long-time scales. The behavior we found was similar to the behavior of a random distribution because packets are separated by random times in certain ranges.

The packets structure can be shown in a more evident way by the representation of the elapsed time between maximum values and counting the number of times it appears, as we show in Figures 4a, 4b and 4c. In these figures the packets structure is represented clearly by means of a minimum in the number of times an elapsed time appears. The intrapacket zone is placed on the left of this minimum, and the interpacket zone on the right of the minimum. In both cases, female and male voices, a peak appears that does not occur in the binary case. That peak, which does not appear in the binary case, has contributions of high frequency noise and high orders of vibration. Therefore, the amplitude of the peak can be reduced by increasing the cutoff.

Fig. 4. Histograms that represents the frequency of apparition of a specific elapsed time. (a)-left up panel- Binary case, (b) -above panel- voice of a woman, (c)-left panel- voice of a man.

The binary model again shows a similar behavior to

that of the human voice. Because of that, we will study other properties of the model to verify if they are present in oral communication.

In the binary model we can recognize different packets because of the different separation we obtain depending on whether we are in a packet or interpacket zone. In the case of the voice we will take the packet separator t_m as the minimum of the representation of time facing frequency of appearance. We can see in Figures 4b and 4c that there is another local minimum t_r that in the binary model can be reproduced as noise of high frequency. For the case of man's voice the values are: $t_r=0.0009$ and $t_m=0.0027$ and for woman's: $t_r=0.0008$ and $t_m=0.0018$. This gives us a rule to decide the elements that form a packet. If $t_i \in [t_r, t_m]$ we will say that it is a typical intrapacket separation time and if $t_i > t_m$ will be a typical interpacket time separation.

5. Series of weights

It is normal to extract time series from series with other contents; flu is a good example. From the time series of flu cases we can have a seasonal series in which the number of flu cases in a season are grouped, without merging seasons, by means of a sum. Thus, we can obtain the empirical rules of transition (causal relations) that link a season to another (Lorenz1963). The same phenomenon takes place for example in the biological generations. In this phenomenon the relation among the number of members in successive generations is analyzed. Once again, to build the new variable we obtain the sum of the members of a generation.

The binary case is similar to the two cases presented previously. The packets appear perfectly differentiated as the successive seasons in the case of flu. Therefore, we can build a series with a new variable which shows a causal relationship. We propose two ways of weighting the content of a packet.

The first one assigns the sum of the covered areas to the weight P_n by bits in the n -th packet. This area is proportional to the number of maximum values in the packet because the bits have the same representation. However, the sum without an order does not characterize directly the information that the packet carries; all the characters with the same number of bits have the same weight. In a byte with two bits to one, more characters can be represented than with a bit to one or with eight bits to one. This effect can be shown by representing the weights (P_n, P_{n+1}) calculated upon a series of random characters that give us a representation of all the possible combinations.

The representation (P_n, P_{n+1}, N) where N is the number of times (P_n, P_{n+1}) appears, is very interesting to reveal internal rules. The number of times a pair appears reveals us the structure of the

binary representation of the ASCII characters as probabilistic rules. An important difference exists between the most probable one-and-zero combinations and the less probable combinations. This can be observed in Figure 5a where a bell-shaped surface appears. This structure is different from the plane surface that should appear when the rules of combination of bits are not applied. If we extract characters from an organized structure, such as a book, and we carry out the same representation, we will observe (Figure 5b) small differences as regards the random case shown in Figure 5a.

Fig. 5. Weights P_n implemented as the sum of the number of 1's (maximum) in a packet (byte). (a) -left panel- random bytes. (b)- right panel- bytes from an organized structure (a book).

The second way of weighting packets is based on the fact that in the binary case the content and the order of the bits are related to the ASCII character (byte) that represents the packet.

In the binary model the problems of weight assignment are resolved by means of the consideration of order inside packets. To keep the internal order we propose the following formula for each packet j :

$$P_j = \sum_{i=1}^{N_j} A_i 2^{\left[\text{int}\left(\frac{t_i}{t_b}\right) - 1 \right]} \quad (5.1)$$

where t_i is the elapsed time between the beginning of the first zero of the packet and the i -th maximum of the packet, A_i is the area of the i -th bit, N_j is the number of bits-to-one in the j packet and t_b the minimum time elapsed between bits. In our model A_i has the same value for all i so that the real value of the area covered by the bit is not important, therefore we assign $A_i = 1$ for all i . In this way we have the actual ASCII value of the packet. The representation of weights that incorporates the number of times a pair appears is significant since, as can be seen in Figure 6, it allows us to differentiate the random case, which has a flat distribution, from the organized case with the internal rules observed in a probabilistic way (probability to pass from a character to another). In this case the surface is not

uniform and presents differences associated with the rules or internal order of the communication.

In the case of oral communication, we consider two families of weight implementation: implementations associated with the number of maximums and implementations related to the areas covered.

5.1 - Number of maximums

The sum of maximums that compose each packet is a simple way of associating a weight with the packet. The result, for the male voice, is shown in Figure 7 (the female case is similar). If no kind of relationship exists between the weight of packets n -th and $n+1$,

Fig.6. The same representation that in the previous case, but now the weight is assigned considering the order of the bits inside the byte. In other words, the weight is the ASCII code of each letter.

the return map will not reveal any special structure. In Figure 7 the rules of packets combination are observed: a packet with a large number of maximums is followed by one with a small number of maximums and, after a small number follows a large number of maximums but also small packets which are the most probable zone.

Fig.7. Similar representation that in the previous case, but now we are in the case of the male voice recorded in the conditions exposed in the text. Again, the weight of each packet is the number of maximums it contains.

Another way of associating a weight is to count the number of maximums in a packet considering the order. In other words, all maximums do not contribute to weight in the same way; it depends on their position inside the packet. This form of weighting can show the existence of rules related to the order of the maximums. In the binary case, the

order, weighted according to the formula(5.1), reproduces the content of the information that carries the packet. In the case of the human voice it does not seem logical to implement the same method because we can identify more than 2 states, so that we implement the following sum:

$$P_i = \sum_{j=2}^{N_i} j(T_j - T_i) \quad (5.2)$$

where T_j is the time that marks the j -th maximum inside the i -th packet, T_i is the time in which the first maximum of the i -th packet occurs, N_i is the number of maximums in the i -th packet and P_i is the weight of the i -th packet. In this formula the values that are separated by a time t in the established limits are considered as maximums; in this way we will study the composition of the packets. Figure 8 shows the structure of the return map of the successive weights. A structure that provides information of the rules of combination of the weights of packets (considering the ordering previously seen), can be clearly distinguished. We see that there are 'forbidden' zones; weights that a packet cannot have. In addition, we can distinguish three well differentiated zones. That of weights greater than 0.015, followed by weights of approximately 0.003. That of weights between 0.0075 and 0.013 that presents two similar behaviors; one like that of the previous zone and the other reproduces the same weight in the following packet. Finally, a zone exists between 0.002 and 0.005. In this zone the following weight can be approximately the same, to be in [0.0075,0.013] or any other value over 0.0015.

Fig. 8. The weight of each packet is calculated according to the formula(5.2). The scale of the representation allow us to observe different zones in the distribution of packets.

To verify that the structure studied has not been introduced by the implementation of the formula(5.2); we simulate a signal with a maximum of 10 peaks by packet in which the time between packets and the number of maximums are randomly generated. The analysis of this information does not reveal the existence of structure induced by the formula. Therefore, the relations that we find between packets appear as new properties.

5.2 - Weights of Maximums

Perhaps the most direct form of assigning weights is to consider the sum of the areas covered below the waves in the packet and the cutoff considered. Figure 9 represents, in arbitrary units, the return map of the successive weights implemented in this manner. We observe in this figure a clustering around the line with a slope of 45° for small weights. Besides, a packet with large weight is followed by another with small weight out of the diagonal zone.

Another possible implementation is to keep the eventual internal order in the packet. In this case, to study the composition of each packet, we propose the following implementation:

$$P_i = \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} j p_j \quad (5.3)$$

where p_j is the weight (covered area) associated with the j -th maximum, N_i is the number of maximums in the i -th packet and P_i is the weight of the i -th packet. The representation, in arbitrary units, is shown in Figure 10. We see a clustering of small weights around the diagonal. The packets considered have a small number of maximums, and therefore of contributions. We can also observe that only a few packets exist with weights over $5 \cdot 10^{-5}$. From this behavior we can deduce that the composition of the packets from the implemented weight is homogeneous and distributed so that a packet with a weight P is followed by another packet with a similar weight. Besides, the zones with large weights are more rarified than those zones in Figure 9. An explanation of this behavior is that the contributions of greater weight inside the packet are found in the first positions. This explains the fact that the packets with many maximums do not show significant differences in weight compared with the remainder packets.

6 Conclusions

In the binary case we have separated the behavior of the protocol that governs the communication from 'contents' using the return map analysis. With these methods we can distinguish types of communication, random or not, within the same protocol. Human voice shows a similar protocol to that of the binary model implemented. Besides, in this protocol some internal rules exist and they are observed in the non-random shape of the relations in the return map. The relations express in a visual way the rules of the communication and, in a colateral way, show that the sampling quality, although low, is sufficient to show interesting structures. This is not an statistical study but shows experiments and methods that gives promising results.

Fig. 9. In this picture the weight of a packet, in arbitrary units, is implemented by means of the sum of enclosed areas by each one of the waves that belong to the packet.

Fig. 10. In this picture the weight of a packet is implemented by means of the formula(5.3)

Gordon Monro et al (Monro1998) in their work of reconstruction of attractors associated with the musical production of certain instruments suggest: "The reconstruction of attractors gives some promise of recovering of information that could be used to model the physics of production of a sound, or cognitive structure underlying a musical design". In our work, methods to show properties and rules of the physics of production of signals, properties and rules of the communication protocol and internal rules associated with the information transmission are implemented. Our methods explore the two levels that constitute the process of communication: the physical and the logical levels. The physical level is explored by means of the analysis of the process periodicity while in the logical level the translation of the communication elements is explored on the physical backup with its internal rules. The existence of internal rules means that the system has retained information of the previous state to configure the following state. All the relations, in maximums or packets, should be maintained to assure the integrity of communication. The implemented ways of weighting are not the unique election: new ways to implement weights in the packets could discover new relations among packets.

Humans are not the only beings that can communicate in an oral way; it is possible to find protocols and rules in animals which use sound

signals. In any case, the methods utilized by us can be implemented in visual signals and in some other ways of communication.

We have shown the existence of new relations among structures (packets). But, we can suppose the existence of new structures that include packets in the same way packets include maximums. Hence, structures of hierarchical levels, and new properties in each level, could appear.

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